

Preliminary Insights of InSAR Applied to the Earthquake Swarm 2020-2021 in the Granada Basin by Using Open Resources

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Abstract

Earthquakes are one of the more destructive natural hazards when their energy is enough to reach inhabited areas. From the end of 2020 to the beginning of 2021, an earthquake series was registered in the district of La Vega, located in the province of Granada which is characterized by the highest seismicity area in the Iberian Peninsula. This event, defined as an earthquake swarm, with specific characteristics as a non-predictable magnitude of its aftershocks, produced damages in the municipalities close to the epicentres of highest magnitudes. The aftershock with the highest magnitude of 4.4 was recorded on 23 Jan. 2021, with epicentre in the northwest part of the municipality of Santa Fe. Given the importance of this phenomenon, this document focuses on precursory research of its territorial effects in the terms of ground deformation. Thus, the displacement map for three different periods (previous to the earthquake series and co-seismic) is obtained by leveraging the currently available open satellite images of Sentinel-1, processed with the use of open-source tools to assess ground movements of low to very low magnitudes (subcentimetric to centimetric scale). Despite the medium resolution of the Sentinel-1 images and the signal constraints by the atmosphere and decorrelation factors, the distribution and general pattern of displacements was revealed by applying the technique Synthetic Aperture Radar Interferometry. They show the clear distribution of the greatest deformation after the co-seismic interferogram generated for the last period analysed (13 Jan. 2021 – 25 Dec. 2021), which contains the date of the earthquake with the highest magnitude. These highest displacements with a downward direction coincide with the municipalities of Pinos Puente, Atarfe and Santa Fe, where the majority of damages were documented. Consequently, the potential of the open resources for the assessment of the surface effects related to low and moderate earthquakes in this specific geographical area was demonstrated. Nevertheless, further research can be addressed to obtain more precise measurements or to deepen into the cause-effect and the expected spatial distribution of damages related to different seismic events.

Keywords: ground deformation, normalized displacements, QGIS, monitoring, fault

1. Introduction and Main Characteristics of The Area of Interest Related to The Active Tectonic

From December 2020 and still, until April 2021, the district of La Vega in the province of Granada has been continuously shaken by hundreds of earthquakes from low to moderate magnitude [1,2]. This phenomenon is referred to as an earthquake swarm, where a large number of seismic events of modest magnitude happen with no identifiable mainshock, so they are not as predictably as aftershock sequences. Aftershock

series follows the mainshock or the first earthquake with the highest magnitude, however, in an earthquake swarm, aftershocks can intensify after slowing down during a few hours or months. Swarms are associated with volcanic, geothermal or, as in this case, tectonic activity. In the target area, a similar sequence was recorded in 1979 [3] with maximum intensities of 6 in the modified Mercalli scale and a magnitude of 5 in the Richter scale [4]. Instead, during the more recent event of 2020-2021, only one earthquake reached a magnitude of 4.4 in the moment magnitude scale (Mw) [5] on 23 January 2021 in the northwest of Santa Fe with intensities reaching the levels V-VI. This earthquake exceeded the magnitude of 3.6 recorded in the previous earthquake on 2 December 2020 in the Lg wave phase-amplitude scale (mblg) [6], with intensities IV-V [7].

The geographical area of interest (AOI), targeted in this document, is located in the southern Spain to the northeast part of the Granada Basin (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Geographical location of the AOI

Southern Spain is the zone of this country with the highest seismicity, which is very noticeable in the Granada Basin, as registered by the historical earthquake record (Table 1). This active seismicity is conditioned by the convergence of the Eurasian and African plates, which has led the geologically rapid uplift of the Betic Cordilleras. This high uplift rate is well represented in the NE-SW antiform of Sierra Nevada, whose height exceeded more than 4000 m since 8-9 million years ago (late Miocene). As a result, a compressive stress field has been developed in the NNW-SSE direction with a tension field in the approximately orthogonal direction (ENE-WSW) [8,9].

YEAR	MAGNITUDE	MAX. INTENSITY	ZONE
Jul. 1431	6.5	IX-X	Atarfe-Granada
4 Jul. 1526	--	VII-VIII	Granada
3 Sep. 1531	6.5	IX-X	Baza (GR)
27 Oct. 1806	5.9	VIII-IX	Santa Fé (GR)
25 Dec. 1884	6.8	X	Arenas del Rey (GR)
29 Dec. 1884	--	VII-VIII	Arenas del Rey (GR)
27 Jan. 1885	--	VII-VIII	Alhama (GR)
14 Mar. 1886	--	VII-VIII	Loja (GR)
31 May 1911	4.9	VII-VIII	Santa Fé (GR)
8 Jan. 1954	4.0	VII-VIII	Arenas del Rey (GR)
19 Apr. 1956	5.0	VIII	Albolote (GR)

Table 1. Historical record of the earthquakes with the highest magnitude in the province of Granada. Modified from [10].

In addition to the structural and geophysical studies revealing the structural patterns of development, high-velocity rates are also well observed in southern Spain by the analysis of GNSS (global navigation satellite system) network data, reaching up to 4.5 mm/year to the south of Spain and North of Africa (area 1 in Figure 2) [11]. Consequently, NW-SE normal faults are favored by the tensional deformations. However, the complex tectonic mechanism of this area has made the extensional field more relevant. Especially, the geographical extension of the Sierra Nevada is dominated by a radial extension pattern as the majority of faults have performed as normal faults.

Figure 2. Horizontal displacement velocity based on a GNSS network for the 2015-2018 interval. Taken from [11].

Many of these fractures in the Granada Basin remain under the sediment as “blind” faults not identified on the ground surface. However, the length and depth of some of these faults have been determined through the analysis of seismological data [12]. A subset of the actual number of active faults affecting the Granada Basin is shown in Figure 3, extracted from the QAFI [13]. It should be noted that not all the faults of the QAFI are related to recent earthquakes, and many other faults that do not outcrop at the surface or are not yet identified can produce earthquakes.

Figure 3. Active faults affecting the Granada Basin.

As a result of this orogenic event, Granada and Guadix-Baza Basins were individualized from the sea during the late Neogene [14]. These basins have been sedimented, reaching a maximum depth of some 2600 m in the depocenter located to the west of Sierra Elvira [15]. Accordingly, the combination of the sediment thickness (at the local scale) with tectonic episodes of differential displacements are the major factors triggering earthquakes in this tectonically active area. These seismic events release energy that is accommodated by the pre-existent faults at the borders and internally to the basins.

In regard to the swarm event of 2020-2021, this paper represents a brief analysis of the findings derived from preliminary research based on an application of the InSAR (Synthetic Aperture Radar Interferometry) technique by using open resources. These resources are referred to as the Sentinel-1 imagery and the processing software SNAP [16]. InSAR consists of the change measurement in the signal phase between two images containing the same geographical area but acquired at different times. The signal phase changes as the ground moves and this effect is used to detect small ground displacements. However, the sensibility of this technique depends on the sensor specifications, acquisition geometry, and target characteristics. In the present application, InSAR is applied to three different consecutive periods covering swarm earthquakes of different magnitudes in the specified AOI, so the performance of this technique by using open resources can be evaluated.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Data

For the purpose of the present analysis the following datasets have been obtained:

- Five single look complex (SLC) images from the Sentinel-1 satellite (Table 2) to cover different periods running before and within the swarm event, to 25 Jan. 2021. More specifically, the Level-1 product of the Interferometric Wide Swath (IW) acquisition mode with dual vertical (DV) polarization (VV-VH) has been used here. These images, which are freely distributed, have been downloaded from the Copernicus Open Access Hub [17]. All of the selected images are in the ascending orbit with the line-of-sight (LOS) pointing to the Est (Figure 4).

Image name	Acquisition date
S1A_IW_SLC__1SDV_20210125T181029_20210125T181056_036298_04422E_EB01	25/01/2021
S1A_IW_SLC__1SDV_20210113T181030_20210113T181057_036123_043C1F_B5F4	13/01/2021
S1A_IW_SLC__1SDV_20201208T181031_20201208T181058_035598_0429D8_CA67	08/12/2020
S1A_IW_SLC__1SDV_20201126T181032_20201126T181059_035423_0423C7_4E74	26/11/2020
S1A_IW_SLC__1SDV_20201114T181032_20201114T181059_035248_041DC4_5A2D	14/11/2020

Table 2. Dataset of the satellite images used.

Figure 4. Footprint of the satellite image dataset (left) and sketch of the LOS in descending and ascending orbits.

- A dataset including the earthquakes of magnitude higher than 1.8 from 14 Nov. 2020 to 25 Jan. 2021. This dataset has been downloaded from the Earthquake Catalogue [7]. Spatial distribution of the seismic dataset is shown in Figure 5a. Additionally, some delineations hypothetically belonging to the same fault planes have been highlighted in Figure 5b. The main criteria to digitize these traces is based on epicentres occurring closer in time and/or space in a quasi-straight linear path parallel to the NW-SE direction, which is consistent with the main orientation of the identified faults of the QAFI. As can be seen, the majority of the epicentres belonging to the earthquakes with the greater magnitude are located between the municipalities of Pinos Puente, Atarfe and Santa Fe, to the north part of the Granada Basin. This is a seismic active border that separates the basin sediments from a calcareous bedrock which is intensely fractured and faulted, that constitutes the mountainous relief of Sierra Elvira to the north of the Granada Basin.

Figure 5. A) Spatial distribution and magnitude of the earthquake dataset. B) Enlarged view with delineations within hypothetical fault planes showing the period within which earthquakes occurred.

The above-described dataset of satellite images has been processed with the following software:

- 3 SNAP v6.0 [16], an open software created by the European Space Agency (ESA) for satellite imagery processing and analysis.
- 4 QGIS v3.16.3 [18], an open-source Geographical Information System (GIS).
- 5 The plugin SNAPHU v2.0.4 [19] for SNAP, an open-source software that transforms the interferometric phase into displacements.

2.2 Methods

Mapping the small deformation of large areas due to different phenomena (earthquakes, subsidence, volcanism, infrastructure failures, among others) it is possible by applying the well-known InSAR technique. InSAR consists of the processing of reflected radar signals which are collected in the off-nadir angle (or look angle) for the same area over different times. It enables the study of the deformation variation, which is useful for many applications such as infrastructure maintenance and natural risk management.

A radar signal is characterized by amplitude and phase. The signal amplitude is related to the backscattered energy, which is highest for stiff and hard natural and artificial objects. In addition, phase depends on the sensor-to-target distance, and thus, it is used to estimate ground displacements along the LOS direction of the signal path.

InSAR, or SAR Interferometry, is the basic technique to measure the signal phase change between two different times over the same area as the distances between the sensor and ground points change, having a specific effect on the phase recorded by the sensor. It is focused on the interferogram generation from the phase difference between two SAR images, or the interferometric phase. To calculate this difference, Eq. (1) [20] is applied by taking into account a ground reference point.

$$\Delta\phi = \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} \frac{B_n}{R \sin \theta} h + \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} \frac{B_n}{R \tan \theta} s + \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} d + \Delta\phi_{APS} + \Delta\phi_\lambda \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

where:

- λ : SAR wavelength
- h : relative ground elevation of targets with respect to a horizontal reference plane
- s : relative slant range position of targets
- d : projection of the relative displacement of targets along the LOS
- B_n : perpendicular baseline
- R : SAR-target distance
- θ : "off-nadir" LOS angle
- $\Delta\phi_{APS}$: atmospheric phase screen or differential tropospheric delay phase contribution

- $\Delta\Phi_\lambda$: phase noise as results of the temporal and geometric decorrelation

By using a digital elevation model (DEM) and precise orbital information, the first and second term of the interferometric phase can be calculated and subtracted. These terms are referred to the topographic phase and the so-called flat-earth phase related to the earth curvature, respectively. Thus, the term related to the target movement (d) can be extracted together with the atmospheric phase screen and the decorrelation noise (Eq. 2), obtaining the differential SAR interferometric phase (DINSAR).

$$\Delta\Phi_d = \frac{4\pi}{\lambda}d + \Delta\Phi_{APS} + \Delta\Phi_\lambda \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

When solving the InSAR equations, two major problems appear. The first one is related to the phase ambiguity. Surface displacements are not directly derived from InSAR. However, the phase difference is determined as the position within one cycle (0° to 360° , 0 to 2π radians, or $-\pi$ to π expressed as a sinusoidal function) corresponding to the 2-way travel of the radar signal when it goes to and returns from the target. That means that each repeating proportion of a wave cycle will produce the same measure, regardless of the number n of cycles ($n2\pi$) that cannot be directly measured, appearing the so-called phase ambiguity. It follows that from Eq. 2, the sensitivity to measures the maximum displacement will depend on the wavelength. Thus, a target displacement in the LOS direction of half-wavelength ($\lambda/2$) will result in the maximum movement being detected without considering decorrelation phase noise and APS effects ($\Delta\Phi_d = 2\pi$).

To determine the additional number of entire cycles to be added to the measured phase, the phase difference between neighbouring pixels has to be integrated through the “phase unwrapping” process [21]. As an interferogram constitutes the two-dimensional map of phase differences respect a reference point, more than one cycle of complete cycles can appear as pixels locates far away from this point. This gives a series of colour fringes repeated for every phase cycle. The zones where the distance between the fringes of the same colour is closer correspond with greater surface deformation. A good example is shown in Figure 6, which shows the fringes generated by combining two Sentinel-1 radar images over the zone affected by the Earthquake (24 August 2016) of Central Italy with a magnitude of 6.1, near Amatrice.

Figure 6. Interferogram showing clear fringes related to the Central Earthquake of Italy, occurred on 24 August 2016. Taken from [22].

In this work the phase ambiguity problem is resolved by applying the Statistical-cost, Network-flow Algorithm for Phase Unwrapping implemented in the SNAPHU plugin [23], enabling the transformation from differential interferometric phase measurements to ground displacements.

The second problem is related to the phase decorrelation noise, which is the more difficult part to be cancelled. In some cases, well and stable meteorological conditions facilitates to model and cancel the APS, as the atmospheric phase show a strong spatial correlation while the target motion is characterized by

strong correlation in time. In addition, temporal decorrelation produces a phase noise when the return signal characteristics become extremely different with time as consequence of rapid changes occurring in the surface targets (vegetation, water, rapid landslides, among other). Temporal decorrelation can also result as a consequence of the geometric decorrelation related to the acquisition geometry (incidence angle) changes so the target reflectivity also varies between sequential acquisitions. This is reduced by selecting images with very similar acquisition geometries (e.g.: the same relative orbit). Additionally, to avoid the processing of areas with a poor signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), a threshold on the coherence is used. Coherence represents a quality measurement of the interferometric phase, which depends on the decorrelation or change in the scattering properties of the measured targets such as reflectance varying over time.

In the present analysis, the following workflow has been performed to obtain the interferometric phase and the ground displacement by using the Sentinel-1 processing tools included in SNAP software:

- 1 Extract the part of the image data (Sub-Swath and bursts) that cover the AOI with the VV polarization. VV polarization is selected here as it is proven to give acceptable results for ground displacement, with high amplitude and good SNR [24].
- 2 Orbit correction by applying Precise Orbit Ephemerides (POEORB) to each image.
- 3 Coregistration to resample the slave image to the reference acquisition geometry of the master image in slant- or ground-range coordinates, and the application of the Enhanced Spectral Diversity (ESD) operator to correct the azimuth shift in the slave image.
- 4 Interferogram formation with sinusoidal values from $-\pi$ to π , as well as the generation of the coherence map with values from 0 (null coherence) to 1 (maximum coherence).
- 5 Subtract the flat-earth and topographic phases.
- 6 Apply the Deburst operator that merges adjacent burst removing seamlines.
- 7 Apply the Goldstein Phase Filtering to increase the quality of the fringes existing in the interferogram.
- 8 Create a subset of the interferogram to constrain the analysis area to the AOI extension.
- 9 Phase unwrapping by using the plugin SNAPHU.
- 10 Phase to displacement conversion.
- 11 Geocode the displacement raster into a map coordinate system by correcting SAR geometric distortions with the aid of a pre-existing DEM.
- 12 Export the phase, coherence, and displacements measurements into netCDF files which are readable by the GIS software.

As above mentioned, in this paper Sentinel-1 data have been used. Sentinel-1 satellites have an acquisition cycle of 12 days, although the same area is revisited every 6 days if the two satellites (1A and 1B) navigating in different orbits are considered [25]. The sensor of the Sentinel-1 satellites operates in the C-band, with a wavelength of approximately 5.6 cm and the incidence angle varies between 20° and 46° [26]. This is the

parameter that constrains the maximum displacement of 2.8 (half of the wave roundtrip), coinciding with one complete sine wave cycle or one wavelength. Another characteristic limiting the smallest angular or linear separation between two objects that can be resolved by this sensor is its ground resolution. The mission Sentinel provides Level-1 products as SLC images with a moderate ground resolution of about 22 m in azimuth (parallel to the flight direction) and 3.5 m in range (perpendicular to the flight direction) directions [27].

After the SAR products are generated, phase and displacements are projected into GIS layouts to compare results, considering three interferograms: before the seismic series, co-seismic with the earthquake on 2 Dec. 2020 and, co-seismic with the earthquake on 23 Jan. 2021. It is worth noting that due to the use of single interferograms, InSAR is more susceptible to decorrelation than other techniques based on the statistical stability of the phase properties through a greater image dataset, commonly, a minimum of 20-25 images [28,29]. Accordingly, to avoid results with a poor SNR, the pixels with a coherence less than 0.55 were masked.

3. Results

In the following, the findings of this preliminary research are presented. As above mentioned, the results from this InSAR application consist of the interferometric phase and displacement mapping, considering the conditions of low to moderate magnitude co-seismic events, as well as a medium resolution and long-wavelength SAR signal. The interferometric (wrapped) phase is used here to identify the zones that were affected by the seismic deformation, while displacement maps show the spatial variation of the earthquake effect. Negative displacements are related to surface targets moving far away from the satellite in the LOS direction, generally related to downwards displacements (subsidence, settlement and mass movements, among others). On the contrary, positive displacements are related to those targets moving towards the satellite position (e.g.: swelling or mass movements). White pixels within the displacement maps have been used to represent the areas with a coherence below the threshold of 0.55.

Accordingly, the interferograms and displacements are shown in Figures 7-10 for the following periods limited by the available SAR images:

- 14 Nov. 2020 to 26 Nov. 2020 (Figure 7), which represents the pre-seismic analysis.
- 26 Nov. 2020 to 08 Dec. 2020 (Figure 8), co-seismic with the starting of the earthquake swarm, containing the earthquake of magnitude 3.6 occurred on 2 December 2020.
- 13 Jan. 2021 to 25 Jan. 2021 (Figure 9-10), co-seismic with the earthquake of magnitude 4.4 occurred on 23 January 2021.

The results of the first period (Figure 7) do not show any phase patterns reflecting co-seismic phenomena. They only reveal some parts where the interferometric phase class matches the highest relief, such as the blue isolated zone to the north of the AOI, which coincides with the mountain of Sierra Elvira (municipality of Atarfe). Nonetheless, in general, displacements are closer to 0 m, matching a period of seismic quiescence before the starting of the earthquake series.

Figure 7. Interferogram (top) and displacement map for the period 14 Nov. 2020 – 26 Nov. 2020 (bottom).

The first signs of change appear in the following period when earthquakes of magnitudes up to 3.6 were recorded (Figure 8). It has to be noted, however, that the distribution of displacements is skewed to the positive domain, with lesser magnitudes to the northwest part of the AOI between the municipalities of Pinos Puente and Atarfe.

Figure 8. Interferogram (top) and displacement map for the period 26 Nov. 2020 – 08 Dec. 2020 (bottom).

Ground changes are even more remarkable considering the last period is considered (Figure 8), including the earthquake of the highest magnitude (4.4). Its corresponding interferogram shows well-formed fringes with wide colour bands, indicating low displacement values. The yellow class is better evidenced to the north (Santa Fe - Atarfe) and northwest (Pinos Puente) of the AOI. This class represents downward movements reaching more than 2 cm, measurements which have not documented or measured with other techniques to date and could be overestimated here for the low to moderate magnitudes of the earthquake swarm.

Figure 9. Interferogram (top) and displacement map for the period 13 Jan. 2021 – 25 Dec. 2021 (bottom).

Despite the limitations of this preliminary application, and given the highest effect related to the 23 January earthquake with magnitude 4.4, together with others of lower magnitude, the displacements generated during the last analysed period (13 Jan. 2021 – 25 Dec. 2021) were then standardized. This was carried out by applying a simple custom script, coded with the QGIS Python console to produce values between -1 (highest negative displacement) and 1 (highest positive displacement). In this way, values are rescaled to be represented into 8 classes, thus enhancing the relative displacement within the AOI. The standardized displacement map is shown in Figure 10. It can be observed the highest values within the interval (-1, 0.75] located in the municipalities of Pinos Puente, Atarfe and Santa Fe. In addition, the standardized map is characterized by a generalization of the negative values, which represent a downward movement, similar to a settlement.

Figure 10. Interferogram (top) and standardized displacement map for the period 13 Jan. 2021 – 25 Dec. 2021.

Discussion and conclusions

The present document constitutes a brief application of InSAR through the use of open resources with the aim of mapping the ground movement effects in relation to the 2020-2021 earthquake swarm in the district of La Vega, which is located in the province of Granada to the south of the Iberian Peninsula. For this scope, the available open data from the Sentinel-1 satellite constellation were exploited, even though low to moderate magnitude earthquakes together with the medium resolution and long-wavelength SAR signal are expected to decrease the sensitivity of this technique. Under these considerations, three periods were evaluated by generating one pre-seismic and two co-seismic interferograms leveraging the processing utilities of SNAP and the plugin SNAPHU.

Interferometric results were then imported and analysed into QGIS. In general, the pre-seismic period did not show ground movement evidence, while an incremental development of fringes appears with the increasing magnitude of the earthquakes in the second and third periods. The highest displacements were detected in the third period, containing the earthquake of 4.4 with an epicenter in the municipality of Santa Fe. These displacements are distributed between the municipalities of Pinos Puente, Atarfe and Santa Fe, matching some of the areas documented as being damaged with the highest intensities, and reaching the levels IV-V [30,31] and even VI [7]. Taking into account the InSAR results after processing the Sentinel-1 dataset, the highest downward displacements show values that exceed 2 cm.

However, it has to be noted that, even though the pixels showing low coherence were filtered, residual phase is still detected as a consequence of the noise produced by atmospheric and decorrelating factors in the area. This can derivate in erroneous or skewed displacements, as those observed in the second period. The total cancellation of the noisy phase is a difficult task, and although deeper processing can be tried, it will not guarantee the improvement of the interferometric phase.

Definitely, the use of open resources for InSAR data processing provides a relevant tool for ground monitoring and the generation of preliminary maps of the seismic effects at a territorial scale that cannot be reached by other techniques (DGPS, continue total station measurement, among others) at a low cost. This is a useful instrument to evaluate seismic risk, which strongly depends on the vulnerability of the constructions, as well as on the susceptibility of the geological settings (sediment and rock strength against external actions, and hydrogeological characteristics). Further research can be done to correlate or model the ground deformation with the dynamical (earthquake acceleration, hydrogeological variables) and static factors (lithology), so the expected damages by earthquakes of greater magnitudes can be estimated. Additionally, more precise maps and point measurements can be obtained if high-resolution images and complex techniques based on DInSAR are applied. One of the most often used techniques is the Persistent Scatterer Interferometry (PSI), based on the analysis of a longer time-series of SAR images, so pixels maintaining a statistically highest coherence throughout the entire series (persistent scatterer) are selected for the processing of the interferometric phase and displacements. This technique, combined with the highest resolution images as those from the Cosmo-SkyMed (Cosmo SkyMed Constellation of small Satellites for the Mediterranean basin Observation), can provide precise and useful information for building and infrastructure monitoring and natural risk management [32]. Thus, a database on time-series of subcentimetric displacements can be generated to make it available to practitioners, scientists and researchers, as can be revised in recent European initiatives [33].

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